

WAYS TO DEVELOP THE ORGANIZATION OF MARKETING RESEARCH IN AGRICULTURE

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Abstract. *In this article, the competitiveness of agricultural products will be sharply increased, the economic efficiency of production will be increased to the optimal level, cluster analysis will be conducted in marketing research, the group of countries with wide export opportunities will be separated, and the countries that import fruits and vegetables will be segmented based on clustering and on the basis of hypothesis. will be considered.*

Keywords: *agricultural products, market, competition, marketing, hypothesis, export, segment, analysis.*

INTRODUCTION

The development of the market infrastructure, along with the improvement of the processes of delivery and sale of agricultural products to consumers, encourages them to produce, store and process more and better products. In order to adapt to the market conditions that arise as a result of such a process, it is important to establish a marketing service in enterprises that grow and process agricultural products, in particular, farms and their councils.

Modernization, first of all, requires technical-technological, spiritual renewal of the network based on re-equipment of production with the most advanced modern technologies. The effective implementation of all activities in this area, defined in the main directions of agricultural modernization, will create an opportunity to raise the economic efficiency of production to an acceptable level based on the sharp increase in the competitiveness of primary agricultural products grown in agriculture. farms, which are considered the main form of economic management. These things can only be done by relying on today's marketing.

Research methodology

Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Conducting marketing research in all sectors of the economy acquires its own complexity. Today, in the agriculture of our republic, farmers and peasant farms, partly agro-firms are operating. It is known that farms produce products mainly for state orders and partly for their own needs (police and horticulture). This, in turn, creates problems related to the production, sale and transportation of products at the lowest cost. The purpose of these studies is to determine the strategy tactics of agricultural enterprises in the market and ensure that they achieve greater success and advantage over competitors.

Analysis and results

Cluster analysis methods are used effectively in marketing research and are among the most common methods. The cluster method is also known as the clustering method in statistics. Cluster analysis of Uzbek scientists is mainly recognized as "statistical grouping" in scientific literature. Many scientific studies have been conducted by scientists of the world and our country on the use of cluster analysis methods in the segmentation of the food products market. Problems related to these have been sufficiently studied by SG'ulomov, SH.Abdullaeva,

SH.Ergashkhodjaeva, M.Kasimova, L.Abdukhalilova, J.Jalolov, Yu.Yusupov, SH.Musaeva and other economists. However, the researches of these scientists were carried out more in the manufacturing and service industries.

The use of cluster analysis in marketing research and its methodological aspects are widely studied in the scientific literature of N. Malhotra, M. Porter and A. Aayker. In particular, N. Malhotra and A. Aayker explained the use of cluster analysis in marketing research using segmentation methods that are mainly implemented in the consumer sector. M. Porter's theories used cluster analysis methods to distinguish specific aspects of countries' competitive advantages and conducted research on the formation of network clusters. V. Smid and Y. Vindlar conducted the first scientific studies on the use of the cluster analysis method in market segmentation. These studies are similar to marketing meta-studies on market segmentation.

It was emphasized that it is necessary to introduce a modern management system in the food and alcohol industry in our country, to increase the volume of production, to increase the type and quality of exported products, and to find new markets with extensive use of marketing and production tools. innovation. The assigned task determines the need to select the most target markets for Uzbekistan and develop marketing strategies aimed at penetrating these markets.

To conduct a cluster analysis, first of all, it is necessary to form information on determining the main competitors of the Republic of Uzbekistan and their position in the world market of juice products. The main source of data is the data of the "Market Access MapITC" database (www.trademap.org), which is the official portal of the International Trade Organization. Developed by ITC to support the needs of exporters, trade promotion institutions, trade policy makers and academic institutions in developing countries. It provides information on customs definitions (including tariff preferences) applied by more than 200 countries and 239 states and territories. In addition,

Taking into account the main purpose of providing marketing services in agriculture, based on demand, supply, price, quality level and other economic indicators, based on the market conditions that may occur at a certain time, all it can be said to use the opportunities effectively. .

To achieve this goal, the following main tasks must be solved:

- to collect information about the markets of agricultural products to determine the changes in supply and demand;
- the selection of a suitable market segment for the targeted activity, allows producers of agricultural products to use them effectively based on their capabilities;
- organization of funds and material resources necessary for implementation of activities, monitoring and evaluation of results.

Farms, councils and even individual farms now have to operate in a competitive market environment. They do not have the ability to independently study the market and conduct special marketing research. Therefore, organizing seminars and consultations for them with the participation of experts from special education and scientific institutions is considered as one of the urgent issues of today. Improving the marketing culture of enterprises and organizations that grow and process agricultural products is one of the activities aimed at increasing the efficiency of their activities. We believe that it is appropriate to take into account the following suggestions when organizing a marketing service for the production of agricultural products:

- organization of adaptation of producers' capabilities to market demands and needs;
- organization of raising the economic knowledge of producers of agricultural

products, that is, farmers and agricultural specialists;

-selection of a responsible employee to conduct marketing service in the production of agricultural products;

At the modern stage of economic development, competitiveness is the only criterion for improving and ensuring the quality of agricultural products and services.

A product to increase competitiveness

(goods and services), is characteristic of the enterprise, the region and the whole country and occupies an important place as the main link of the economy.

Work in the field of agriculture in the market economy agricultural enterprises to success reach effective development of economic activity and careful planning of one's opportunities and prospects depends on being armed with the necessary information about

Among the important conditions for the emergence of competition in the conditions of the modern market economy, the following can be included:

complete economic (economic) independence of each product-producing and service-providing firm;

the full dependence of the producer's activity on the market situation;

face all other producers of goods in competition for demand.

Currently, there are different directions of researching the concept of "competitiveness". The famous Austrian economist Y. Schumpeter, the founder of the evolutionary theory of economic development, described competition as a struggle between the new and the old.

The main purpose of cluster analysis in marketing research is to identify a group of countries with great export potential. The grouping of countries based on objectively determined criteria is based on the assumption of some degree of homogeneity for exporting enterprises. Based on this hypothesis, clustering is divided into 5 main areas of fruit and vegetable importing countries. The "Ward" method of hierarchical clustering is used, assuming that the measurement units have different forms according to the selected criteria. This method divides countries into groups based on the spread of values for selected criteria. Using the "Ward" method, countries are divided into 5 main segments.

The competitiveness of the enterprise is the ability to achieve effective economic activity and profit in a competitive market.

Competitiveness of an enterprise is a set of characteristics that reflect the superiority of an economic entity over a competing enterprise in terms of indicators such as financial and economic, marketing, production, technological, personnel potential and ecology in certain market conditions. . This is the ability of the business entity to operate without crisis and quickly adapt to the changing external environment. English economist A. Smith, a famous representative of the classical school, explained competition as a behavioral category. Individual sellers and buyers compete in the market to profitably sell and buy, respectively. Competition is the "invisible hand" of the market and regulates the activities of its participants. The purpose of competition is to make more profit.

A. Smith's contribution to the development of the theory of competition can be shown in the priority directions of farm development: achievements, experiences and prospective plans. He was one of the first to define competition as struggle. The main principle of competition is the principle of "invisible hands". He developed a competitive mechanism that theoretically equalizes the rate of profit in a network, leading to an efficient allocation of resources between networks.

Given the existence of a large number of sellers and buyers, he defined the basic conditions of effective competition, which did not allow each seller to significantly influence the change in the market price of the commodity.

The competitiveness of the enterprise includes the price and quality of agricultural products, as well as the regulation of the flow of financial resources, the level of management. The level of competitiveness is affected by various situations that occur in one or another market, such as the introduction of innovations, financial stability, motivation of employees with advanced methods and methods, division into categories.

Effective marketing activities play an important role in increasing the competitiveness of an agricultural company. Because it is marketing that is aimed at realizing the most necessary requirements of buyers, taking into account changes in consumer tastes, and forming effective and practical methods of increasing competitiveness.

Table 1

Product competitiveness indicators			
No	Naming	Explanation	An example
1.	Normative	How well the product meets the standards and requirements established by law response rate	Compliance with minimum requirements, DAST, etc
2.	Technician	Purchase removable and directly known need to satisfy refer of goods feature and description	Available on certain parameters to the descriptions suitable coming in use amenities, service life, service show duration etc
3.	Economical	What the consumer does in the process of buying the product and using it in the future expenses monetary value	Selling price based on product description The cost of materials and spare parts necessary to maintain the condition of use

One of the important conditions of competitiveness is the quality of the offered product, which is able to meet the needs of the population for agricultural products to one degree or another. Quality management of agricultural products plays an important role in ensuring the competitiveness of an agro-firm. Modeling of the competitive performance of the product is carried out at the stage of its design. The ability to fully satisfy the requirements of customers compared to the products of competitors in the market indicates the competitiveness of the product. The ratio between product quality, service level and prices is the basis for ensuring the competitiveness of agricultural products in the market. In addition, various factors: advertising, brand reputation, etc.

The non-availability of the necessary technical service for the goods sold by the agricultural company leads to the loss of competitive advantage. Therefore, in order to ensure the

competitiveness of the product, it is necessary to provide service to the goods even after they are sold. If such supply is denied, the consumer will seek help from competitors and cause him to switch completely to the competitor's side. Therefore, in order to increase competitiveness, the enterprise must clearly and precisely plan the service system, taking into account all the possibilities of technical support.

In the marketing practice of enterprises, it is appropriate to use cluster analysis methods in the analysis of the competitive environment, segmentation, pricing, and product strategy development. The use of the cluster analysis method in the effective capture and segmentation of global markets increases the effectiveness of marketing research.

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